

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF LITERARY TEXTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ТЕКСТОВ В РАЗВИТИИ УСТНОЙ РЕЧИ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

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Abstract

The article elaborates the use of literary texts in the development of oral speech in English. The main goal in language teaching is to adequately develop the four skills - reading, writing, speaking, listening. In reaching this goal, short texts -short stories, fairy tales, fables, puzzles, diaries, etc.- which are the products of literature and literature can be used as a tool in the development of students' skills. Because literature not only helps students understand the culture, language and people of a country, but also enables them to reach their "emotion-mind balance" individually. The students can only experience the use of this language through literary texts and acquire information about the language, life and culture of that country.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается использование художественных текстов в развитии устной речи на английском языке. Основная цель в обучении языку - адекватно развить четыре навыка - чтение, письмо, говорение, аудирование. Для достижения этой цели в качестве средства развития умений учащихся могут быть использованы короткие тексты — рассказы, сказки, басни, ребусы, дневники и т. д., которые являются произведениями литературы и художественной литературы. Потому что литература не только помогает учащимся понять культуру, язык и людей страны, но и позволяет им достичь своего «баланса эмоций и разума» индивидуально. Студенты могут испытать использование этого языка только через литературные тексты и получить информацию о языке, жизни и культуре этой страны.

Keywords: short texts, culture, oral speech, literature, comprehension, language skills

Ключевые слова: короткие тексты, культура, устная речь, литература, понимание, языковые навыки

Today, it is no longer possible to live as a closed society within its own geography in a world where borders are almost removed. The importance of learning and teaching a foreign language is as up-to-date and clear today as it was yesterday. It is assumed that everyone knows a foreign language in the business world, and people who know a second or even more foreign languages are preferred. In the globalizing world, there is a broad globalization in economy, tourism and education. In such an environment, it is seen that the learning and teaching of a foreign language is gaining increasing importance. In today's world, where communication is at the forefront, besides the traditional teaching methods used before, it has gained more importance to raise individuals who are compatible with the social and cultural world by making use of newer methods. The first goal is to raise an enlightened society that is student-centered, in which communication is at the forefront, that brings cultures and societies closer to each other, and acts as a bridge in foreign language teaching. People who learn and speak a foreign language form a bridge between cultures and societies, ac-

quire a different perspective on the language and culture of their country, and become enlightened individuals who act as a bridge without breaking away from their own culture and language. These individuals become aware of their own culture, get to know another culture closely, and enable us to understand what is not ours.

Among the main objectives of today's language education, besides communication, it plays an important role in understanding the religion, language, culture, history, literature of the other party, in short, the way of life. Due to the importance of learning a foreign language, many new methods have been developed, and new materials have been used to keep people's interest alive [2]. Literature and materials that are the products of literature also have a privileged place in language teaching. It is important to work with literary texts and to use literary texts in foreign language teaching, because both the content and methods and techniques of literary texts are suitable for language teaching methods and courses. We can easily use this in the

development of four skills in language teaching. Literary texts also show students the target culture as well as the target language.

Recently, literary texts are seen as one of the basic parts of foreign language teaching and are included in the curriculum preparation process as a source of authentic texts. The use of literary texts has become very common in order to teach the four basic skills (reading, listening, speaking, writing) and language use (vocabulary, grammar, correct pronunciation) required in foreign language teaching.

In addition, in the translation department of many universities that exist both in Azerbaijan and abroad today, academicians want their students to translate poems, theater texts or short stories into their mother tongue. In this way, by translating these literary texts, students can learn both the four skills they learned during their English language education; and they have the opportunity to practice in areas such as vocabulary and sentence knowledge.

We can say that there are certain reasons why literary texts are primarily preferred as a source in foreign language education and that these texts are used. In Collie and Slater's book, *Literature in Language Classrooms*, these reasons are listed as follows: [5].

1. Valuable and original material
2. Cultural enrichment
3. Linguistic enrichment
4. Individual participation

We can show the reasons given below as an example for the use of literary texts in lessons [1, p.109];

- Literature offers great potential for interesting learning environments. A short story, novel or poem can be read anywhere. On the other hand, it is not easy to use the dialogues we learn from grammar books in real life.

- Working with literary texts provides authentic communication opportunities. In other words, it prepares you realistic environments that match the real world.

- Since literary texts introduce cultural environments closely, they directly contribute to the development of language learners' social skills and education.

Gerhardt Helbig also mentions different reasons for the use of literary texts in his work "German as a Foreign Language". These are [3];

- It increases the joy of reading,
- It provides an opportunity for communication,
- It promotes cognitive, social and emotional competences.

Indeed, if the teacher carefully selects, prepares and adapts the literary texts in the foreign language teaching lesson, it can be more effective, meaningful and instructive than the dry texts in the textbooks. Because students can actively participate in such studies and express themselves creatively. He is able to develop his skills, to empathize and to look from a different point of view thanks to literature. For students who will acquire a foreign language as a profession, it is indispensable to use grammar correctly in the learning and teaching processes of that language. This situation highlights the selection and learning of literary texts in

foreign language classes, which is suitable for use because every literary text passes through this filter. However, whatever the reason is, literature and short texts are a useful resource for students in every situation such as language teaching with the help of literary texts, even learning or teaching literary texts through language.

Here we see linguists such as French C. Marcel, P Passy, English Prendergast, Sweet and German Wilhelm Vietor [6]. Some of these linguists thought that they would learn a foreign language as well as their mother tongue, and they adopted the Grammar-Translation method, which has survived to the present day, especially when learning Latin. According to this method, writing and reading skills are emphasized and activities that develop these skills are carried out. Here, "the content of the text is not given much importance. However, the content of the text is an exercise for grammar and vocabulary analysis. In other words, the sentence patterns, words and word groups in the text are more important than the ones described in the text. Because the main purpose of this method is to teach the rules of the language and to be able to translate correctly through these rules".

As it is seen, the literary text is not the goal but the tool here. It can be said that with the help of literary texts, students' reading comprehension skills, vocabulary and writing skills are improved. With the help of literary texts, besides the development of the translation skills of the students, at the end of the reading texts that will improve their reading skills, reading comprehension and inference So they will be able to answer questions that will help to make a connection between their own experiences and the text.

At the same time, their vocabulary will develop and their vocabulary will be enriched by means of synonyms and antonyms. Here, similar words between the target language and the mother tongue can also help. Grammar rules are shown to students by deduction method. For example, the formation of a sentence such as S + V + O may be asked to find the equivalents in the text. At the same time, the students can be asked to put the correct answers in multiple-choice form by leaving gaps in the sentence with the fill-in-the-blank method. Students can be asked to memorize the native language equivalents of the words in the text and reinforce them by using them in new sentences. At the same time, the writing of the students can be improved, and writing exercises can be made about the theme, subject and title of the reading text with the help of the words they have learned. With this method, the student "makes progress in terms of reading and writing skills. But he has problems in terms of speaking and listening skills".

1. Valuable and Original Material

When it comes to literature, the first thing that comes to mind is originality, being original. Therefore, the purpose of writing literary texts by authors is not primarily to contribute to language teaching, but recently the contribution of these texts to language teaching has become undeniable. Today, many publishing houses and many book authors prefer to use authentic materials. D. Nunan defines authentic materials as:

“Any material not specifically produced for language teaching purposes”. The texts in question were defined by M. Peacock as “material prepared to realize some social purposes in the society speaking the target language”. These materials are written and arranged on the language we use in daily life and aim to expose students to the real life environment and to feel the external environment and atmosphere that exists there [4]. In addition, even if students who are learning a new language have difficulty at first when they read a text written in a foreign language, they will see the use of that language and the use of different phrases and patterns over time. It is of great importance for students to see different usage areas of a language in order to make progress in language learning.

2. Cultural Enrichment

For students learning a foreign language as a second language, the best and most useful way to learn that language is to live in the country where that language is spoken, visit or learn about that country. Because in this way, students will have the opportunity to see the dialogues and physical conditions in literary texts such as theater plays, novels, and short stories. This will be a guide for students to understand how communication takes place in that country. Although it is accepted that the atmosphere in many literary works is imaginary, students can reconcile the environments and character descriptions depicted in the work, and they can easily visualize it in their minds when they visit that country. This colorful world he creates in his mind can provide the reader with the perception of how a real society is formed from a visual point of view.

3. Linguistic Enrichment

Literature helps students learn individual syntax and word structure from many different fields. In this way, students become familiar with many grammatical features of written language. They can also understand the syntax and discourse features of sentences by seeing many different structures (like possible different structures, different ways of connecting ideas, or transitions between ideas). Learning these structures and trying to use them allows students to improve their writing skills [4]. In this way, students can be productive and creative at the same time. Because they begin to grasp the richness and diversity of the language while writing. In addition, they develop their communicative and cultural skills through the richness of original materials.

4. Individual Participation

It is not possible for us to ignore the existence of literature during language learning. Because the existence of literature during language learning also affects the degree of individual participation of students in the process. When a student starts to read a text written in a foreign language, he not only reads the text but also finds himself in that text. While examining a text, it is affected by the environment created in the text and integrates the text with its own existence. In addition to focusing on the words, expressions or structures in the text, the course of the story and the events that develop in the story can also attract attention. As students wonder what will happen on the next page as they turn each page, their desire to read increases. During reading, students can identify themselves with some characters and

find common ground with their own emotional states by sharing their feelings. From this point of view, it is of great importance to select literary texts according to students' needs, expectations, language levels and interests.

In addition to these items, there are other reasons for using literary texts in language teaching. One of these reasons is the universality of literary texts. Literature mostly deals with the common values of humanity. The events that occur in the work are the events that can happen to all people on earth, and the themes of these events are common themes such as death, love, separation and nature. The subjects that human beings can experience during their lifetime form the basis of literature. Therefore, literary works are considered to be universal.

Another item is the diversity of literary texts. If we examine the literary texts in detail, it is possible to see that they were written on a wide variety of subjects. Since literary texts are original materials, as we mentioned before, they provide information on different subjects, from daily subjects to academic subjects. For example, when reading a text on law, the student can become familiar with and have knowledge of many legal terms. Or, if the text he reads is related to psychology, he will have information about psychology and can learn some terms related to psychology.

Finally, individual interaction and attention is another reason why literary texts are used in language teaching. Since literary texts deal with thoughts, feelings and events, they can be situations that touch the reader's life, or they can be about imaginary situations. The reader can associate what he reads in the text with his own life. In addition, literary texts are often based on topics and themes that people find inherently interesting. Since they are mostly able to appeal to the experiences or thoughts that the readers have, they are likely to attract the attention of the reader in this way.

As a result, the role of literature, and therefore literary texts, is very important in language teaching. However, at this point, the role of the teacher should not be forgotten. First of all, the teacher should determine the needs and expectations of the students well. Then, he should determine the language teaching method, techniques and activities suitable for the purposes he has determined. In the next step, the teacher should choose the literary texts that he/she aims to use, the way these texts are conveyed to the students, according to the purposes and methods that he/she has previously determined, because the needs, expectations and foreign language level of the students at all levels are not the same. The above-mentioned issues should be taken into account when choosing literary texts and incorporating these texts into the curriculum.

Literature is the place where students can encounter different structures and culture of the language they learn in foreign language teaching. Teachers' assistant can be literary texts alongside technology. Working with literary texts can be done from the very beginning to the end of the learning, and it can be used effectively and actively by choosing appropriate texts for the level of the student. With the literary text that the teacher

brings to the classroom, students are given the opportunity to establish a connection with literature through studies aimed at improving their reading, writing, speaking and even listening skills in the visual and auditory form of the literary text recorded by the speaker in the relevant language. Foreign language learners build a bridge with a second culture and language other than their mother tongue and culture, and have the opportunity to look at the language and culture of their country from a different perspective. As can be seen, literary texts can be used easily at all stages of language learning. Literary text is a tool, not a goal here, it contributes to the expansion of students' vocabulary and grammar. In language teaching, texts can be shortened, expanded or even changed according to needs, they can be shaped according to students' own imaginations and interpreted differently. However, if there are situations where the literary text is a purpose other than being a tool, the student enters the situation of teaching literary text through language, not language teaching through literary text, in such cases it is carried out of purpose and it may not be possible to reach the goal. The teacher needs to avoid this and needs to identify this from the very beginning when setting goals. In our opinion, a language course in which literary texts are used as a tool will be productive, successful and satisfying with

a free, participatory and student-centered language teaching that can be viewed from such a broad perspective.

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Abstract

The work aims to determine the difference in opinions and viewpoints of elementary school students about a multicultural environment and youth violence, taking into account gender, grade level, and school success. The sample consisted of eighth and ninth-grade elementary school students (N=215) from Serbia. The results of the research show that the students' opinions on characteristics, educational outcomes, and youth violence do not statistically differ significantly when the independent variables are taken into account. The students' attitudes towards the values of living together in a multicultural environment and the school's influence on the prevention of violence caused by differences in different cultures do not differ significantly when the independent variables are taken into account.